

Ichnofabric for Stratigraphic Analysis: an outcrop study in Samarinda Area, Kutai Basin, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

The identification of demarcation surfaces of ichnofabric criteria is introduced here with reference to outcrops study in Samarinda Area, Kutai Basin Indonesia. Accordingly, the ichnofabric criteria such as ichnotaxa, tiering styles, BI (bioturbation index), diversity, burrow diameter, and penetration depth are gathered, processed, analyzed. Consequently, the three ichnofabric criteria include (1) the changes from section composed predominantly of ichnofossil to another one that absent of ichnofossil or vice versa, (2) the changes of multiple tiering styles to single tiering styles or vice versa, (3) the changes of internal tiering styles within of the single tiering style section are resulted. Moreover, those criteria are representative of three demarcation surfaces that proposed.

Key words: ichnofabric, demarcation surfaces, stratigraphic surfaces, tiering.

INTRODUCTION

Stratigraphy is techniques for the reconstruction of earth history into a coherent view of how the earth works and its life forms evolved by integration of variability of the data (after Posamentier and Allen, 1999; Catuneanu, 2006; Embry, 2009). However, the challenge is how to demarcate that environmental history by chronologic criteria in the rock record that called stratigraphic surfaces or keybed. Accordingly, ichnofossil is one of the data of that has been developed for stratigraphic analysis that can be referred in Bromley (1975); Savrda (1991); Bromley and Goldring (1992); MacEachern, et al (1992); Pemberton, et al (1995); Taylor, et al (2003).

Moreover, the history of environmental fluctuation (e.g. oxygen, substrate stability, substrate consistency, particulate organic matter) has been demonstrated by Ari-

Figure 1 The location map of outcrop studies in Samarinda Area (From Google Earth 2016).

Table 1. The ichnofabric criteria of demarcation surfaces

No	Criteria
1	The shifting of section composed predominantly of ichnofossil to another one that absent of ichnofossil or vice versa.
2	The reshaping of multiple tiering styles to single tiering styles or vice versa (figure 2).
3	The modification of internal tiering styles within of single tiering style section (figure 3).

fullah, et al. (2016) and previously by Savrda and Bot-tjer (1987, 1989, 1994), who focused on oxygen fluctuation. Accordingly, that fluctuation can be delineated by demarcation surfaces that will be introduced here with

reference to outcrops study in the Samarinda Area, Kutai Basin, Indonesia (figure 1).

Although conversely ichnofossil can be observed in Kutai Basin, the incorporation the ichnological criteria for stratigraphic analysis is lacking (e.g., Bachtiar, 2004; Arifullah, 2005). Owing to the fact that, this paper initiates the usage of ichnological criteria for that.

DATA AND METHODS

The fundamental ichnofabric data such as: ichnotaxa, tiering styles, BI (bioturbation index), diversity, burrow diameter, and penetration depth are gathered that methods of data collecting can be accessed in Arifullah, et al. (2016). Moreover, he decodes ichnofabric trends vertically. Consequently, some interpretations such as substrate stability, substrate consistency, bedload and

Figure 2 The 2nd ichnofabric criteria of demarcation surface from Mahkota outcrop in the southern Samarinda Area. **A.** Single tiering that dominated by *Thalassinoides* and modest of *Planolites*. **B.** Multiple tiering, upper tiering includes *Paleophycus*, *Macanopsis*, *Rhizocorallium*; middle tier includes *Zoophyzos*, *Teichichnus*, *Spirophyton* and *Ophiomorpha*; lower tier includes *Chondrites*. **C.** Single tiering that dominated by *Ophiomorpha* and modest of *Thalassinoides*, *Paleophycus*, and *Siphonichnus*.

Figure 3 The 3rd ichnofabric criteria of demarcation surface from Tamansari outcrop in the southern Samarinda Area. This demarcation surface indicates the modification of the internal tiering styles within of single tiering style section between B and A intervals. **A.** Single tiering that dominated by *Ophiomorpha* and modest of *Siponichnus*, *Macaronichnus* and *Paleophycus*. **B.** Single tiering that includes *Paleophycus* and modest of *Rosselia* and *Helmintoidichnites*. **C.** Multiple tiering, upper tiering dominated by *Ophiomorpha*, and modest of *Thalassinoides* and *Macanopsis*, lower tiering dominated by *Macaronichnus* and

suspended load, oxygen fluctuation, particulate organic matter (POM) and identification of community succession have been resulted.

Accordingly, (Arifullah, et al, 2016) show implicitly the simple stratigraphic surfaces (e.g, the abrupt changes from section that composed predominantly of ichnofossil to another one that absent of ichnofossil or vice versa) can be observed directly in the rock record. Consequently, if a given set of ichnofabric descriptive

criteria therefore every geologist can generate the comparable determination for the same of rock.

An additional point to keep in mind, stratigraphic surfaces that based on ichnofabric criteria are not always coincident with other stratigraphic surfaces that based on lithofacies or biofacies criteria. The simplest method to create the ichnofabric criteria in deciding of stratigraphic surfaces is characterizing such as shown in table 1. The first criteria may be easy to observed. However, watchful when observe the “massive” rock that connotated as no bioturbation that frequently camouflage their ichnofabric features. For the examples, small and resemble of burrow fill and lining colour of *Macaronichnus* with the surrounding rock, preservation of undertrack in lamina contact in shale unit, *Chondrites* and *Phycosiphon* in the laminae, mottled or homogenized that product of tracemaker stirring. Thus, taphonomic reason influence the quality of ichnofossil preserved in the rock record (Bromley, 1996; Savrda, 2007).

Table 2. The types of tiering style

Type	Criteria
1	The single tiering with identical ichnotaxa.
2	The single tiering with variable ichnotaxa that represented by identical ethology.
3	The single tiering with variable ichnotaxa that represented by different ethology.
4	The multiple tiering.

Figure 4 *Macaronichnus* interval from Tamansari outcrop in southern Samarinda Area. **A.** The *Macaronichnus* interval is bordered by dotted lines. **B.** The sedimentary log of Tamansari outcrop incorporates lithofacies and ichnofabrics (tiering diagram) criteria. *Macaronichnus* is developed only in the red dotted line interval and interrupts the overall usual ichnofabrics.

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Trans Luxury Hotel, Bandung, October 10 – 13, 2016

Figure 5 The ichnofossil association of *Macaronichnus* ichnofabric from Tamansari outcrop, southern Samarinda Area. **A.** *Macaronichnus* (Ma), *Ophiomorpha* (Op), *Scaubicylindrichnus* (Sb) that shows the truncated branch, *Chondrites* (Ch). **B.** *Macaronichnus* (Ma). **C.** *Macaronichnus* (Ma) indicates the characteristic of burrow fill. **D.** *Ophiomorpha* (Op) displays the truncated branch, *Chondrites* (Ch).

Figure 6 Ichofossil associates with scouring surfaces. A. The dotted line demarcates brown shale and fine-medium sandstone lithofacies. B. *Diplocraterion* (Di) has been identified in the brown shale lithofacies. *Diplocraterion* shows sharp burrow lining and contrast burrow fill with surrounding lithology. C. The dotted line demarcates gray silty shale and coarse sand lithofacies. D. Gray silty shale comprises *Thalassinoides* (Th), *Skolithos* (Sk) and coarse sand colonized by *Ophiomorpha* (Op).

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Trans Luxury Hotel, Bandung, October 10 – 13, 2016

Moreover, the determination of the second and third criteria is required for an observer to scrutinize the tiering styles of ichnofabric. Accordingly, the observation of 400's meters of outcrops in Samarinda Area generates four tiering styles (table 2). Having knowledge of the definition and nature of tiering can be accessed on Ekdale (1985) and Bromley (1996).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The demarcation surfaces

The 1st demarcation surface implies the shifting of the environment at a broader scale than other criteria. Since the intensity of ichnofossil represents the mobility (Rhoads, 1975), thus practically the section that contains ichnofossil represent the existence of mobility than that one absent of ichnofossil that may be ecologically represent stressful environment (Gray and Elliot, 2009). Those environments are different means of physical, chemical and biological characteristics.

The 2nd demarcation surface (figure 2) implies the reshaping of the environment locally. The multiple tiering indicates equilibrium community environment (Ekdale, 1985; Ekdale and Bromley, 1991; Bromley, 1996; Taylor, et al. 2003) than single tiering that indicates disturbance environment (Gray and Elliot, 2009) and short live event (Ekdale, 1985; Taylor, et al. 2003).

The 3rd demarcation surface (figure 3) implies the modification rapidly of the environment locally. Single tiering is represented by 1st, 2nd, and 3rd type of tiering (table 2) that has criteria that "ethology" is the keyword. Ecologically, that one represents the capacity and capability of tracemaker to tolerance rapidly with highly disturb and fluctuated environment (Ekdale, 1985; Gray and Elliot, 2009).

Sometimes, the unusual environmental event interrupts the overall usual environmental conditions. That event is marked by a demarcation bed that represented by the build up of unique ichnofossil content that founded in Tamansari outcrop, southern part of Samarinda Area. Accordingly, that ichnofossil is called a *Macaronichnus* ichnofabric beds (figure 4, 5) that dominated by *Macaronichnus*, and modest ichnofossil such as *Ophiomorpha*, *Skolithos*, *Siphonichnus*, *Paleo-*

phycus, *Scaubcylindrichnus*, *Rhizocorallium*, *Teichichnus*, and minor ichnofossil such as *Taenadium*, *Astero-soma*, and *Chondrites*.

Moreover, those ichnofabric bed is associated with the hummocky cross stratification (HCS) and swaley cross stratification (SCS) lithofacies unit with 1,7 meters thick. Generally, HCS and SCS lithofacies sets imply the physical process that suggested as a storm event product. Nevertheless, how the contribution of ichnofabric criteria does. Moreover, the occurrence of those ichnofabric shortly after deposition may be reveal the colonization of the opportunist community (Ekdale, 1985; Gray and Elliot, 2009), and utilization of the duration of time potentially available for colonization to take place and for a burrow system that defined as colonization window (Pollard, et al. 1993) that reflect the environmental stability (Taylor, et al. 2003).

The revisiting to the Glossifungites ichnofacies

The concept of *Glossifungites* is still enigmatic (Gingras, et al, 2000). As firmground ichnofacies, *Glossifungites* is constructed in dilatancy substrate that compaction or dewatering has been occurring (e.g., Gingras, et al, 2000) in exposed mudflat deposit after sandflat scoured (Arifullah, 2005). Consequently, the ichnological characters of *Glossifungites* are not different with other ichnofossil such as *Thalassinoides*, *Diplocraterion*, *Rhizocorallium*, *Teichichnus* or deep tiering ichnofossil such as *Scolicia*, *Zoophycos* or even *Chondrites* that indicates excavation and backfilled strategy to build in dilatancy substrate (after Bromley, 1996). All of them characterized by sharp burrow walled and contrast burrow fill with the surrounding rock. It is realized that why the member of *Glossifungites* is the stiff nature of substrate ichnofossil such as *Rhizocorallium*, *Diplocraterion*, *Thalassinoides*, *Arenicolites* and *Skolithos* (Pemberton and MacEachern, 1995). Consequently, the *Glossifungites* ichnofacies is not exclusive.

Moreover, the outcrop observation in Samarinda Area indicates the ichnofossil that build by excavation strategy such as *Thalassinoides*, *Skolithos*, and *Diplocraterion* (figure 6) that imply the 3rd or 1st demarcation surfaces (table 1). It may be signified as *Glossifungites*

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GEOSEA XIV CONGRESS AND 45TH IAGI ANNUAL CONVENTION 2016 (GIC 2016)

Trans Luxury Hotel, Bandung, October 10 – 13, 2016

ichnofacies if those demarcation surfaces are proven as sequence boundary. However, we must not parsimoniously apply the *Glossifungites* terminology.

CONCLUSIONS

Since ichnofabric imply the tracemaker and substrate interaction in space and time, therefore the ichnofabric criteria can be optimized for reconstruction of earth history into a logical view of how the earth works and its life forms. Accordingly, the simple demarcation surfaces based on ichnofabric criteria are proposed that can be detected directly in the rock record. Moreover the interpretation of that is restricted to why and how the nature of demarcation surfaces is by the reference of ichnofabric criteria.

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